

Why climate adaptation could be the movement's missing mobiliser

Discussion paper

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About the series

This is the second in a series of discussion papers exploring where the climate movement might focus its energy and resources. Each paper examines a different frontier for climate organising, developed in collaboration with thinkers and strategists from across the movement. Our goal is to spark debate, share evidence from recent campaigns, and help organisers make choices about where to invest limited movement resources. The [first paper](#), co-authored with Maciej Muskat from Greenpeace International, examined the potential of activism around extreme weather events. This paper, co-authored by Rupert Read, Co-Director of the [Climate Majority Project](#), and Cathy Rogers, Director of Research and Development at [Social Change Lab](#), asks whether climate adaptation - long neglected by the movement - might in fact be a powerful tool for building the broad-based, politically potent constituency that campaigners have long sought.

Keywords: climate adaptation, strategic adaptation, climate resilience, maladaptation, social movements, political mobilisation.

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Cover image: Retrofit Balsall Heath - neighbours attending a housing protest march campaigning for retrofitting and better housing standards. Available [here](#).

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Ask people in Fishlake, where [floods in 2019](#) destroyed 100 homes, what climate change means. They won't talk about CO2 parts per million. They'll talk about a lifetime of accumulated possessions ruined, months in temporary accommodation, and insurance premiums that tripled. They'll talk about lying awake in fear during heavy rainfall.

This is Britain's climate. It's time to face it.

What if the most powerful way to do that was hiding in plain sight? What if there were a way to face it which also brings neighbours together, reduces energy costs, makes homes warmer in winter (and cooler in summer), gives people a reason to show up at council meetings, improves mental wellbeing, cleans up and beautifies rivers, reduces flood risk - and builds the kind of broad-based political constituency that the climate movement has spent decades trying to create. It doesn't require people to label themselves as environmentalists. It doesn't need party political framing. It starts with what people already care about - their homes, their streets, their children's health - and it works.

It's time to take climate adaptation seriously.

Telling it like it is

We are not going to keep global heating below agreed targets. The 1.5°C Paris Agreement goal is, for practical purposes, already gone: 2024 was the first year to exceed 1.5°C above the pre-industrial average, and the [Met Office forecasts](#) that 2026 will be the fourth consecutive year above 1.4°C. The [UN Environment Programme's 2025 Emissions Gap Report](#) is blunt: even if every country meets its latest climate pledges (which will of course not happen), the world faces 2.3 to 2.5°C of overheating. Under policies currently in place, we're heading for at least 2.8°C. The gap between what's needed and what's happening is not closing - it has [barely moved in four years](#). And of course the geopolitical headwinds against decarbonisation are now desperately strong.

This matters because the consequences aren't hypothetical - they're here. In the summer of 2022, UK temperatures exceeded 40°C for the first time. The heatwaves caused an

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estimated [2,985 excess deaths](#) in England - overwhelmingly among the over-65s. The NHS saw a [spike in 999 calls](#), hospitals cancelled surgeries because operating theatres overheated, and care services for the elderly were pushed to breaking point. The London Fire Brigade [declared a major incident](#) with its busiest day since the Second World War. Railway tracks [buckled](#), roads melted, Luton Airport suspended flights after heat damaged the runway, and Network Rail issued a blanket ['do not travel' warning](#) out of London. Between 2016 and 2021 alone, Network Rail spent [£51 million on compensation payments](#) due to high temperatures. Without adaptation, the UK's Climate Change Risk Assessment estimates heat-related deaths could rise to [7,040 per year by 2050](#).

Flooding risks are just as stark. The [Environment Agency's 2024 National Flood Risk Assessment](#) found that 6.3 million properties in England are now in areas at risk of flooding - up 15% from its previous 2018 assessment. With climate breakdown, that figure could reach 8 million by mid-century, putting one in four properties in England at risk. The Association of British Insurers saw a [record £585 million in home weather-damage payouts](#) in 2024. An estimated [70,000 homes have been built on flood-risk land since 2009](#) - and because the [Flood Re](#) insurance scheme, a joint initiative between government and the insurance industry, only covers homes built before that date, many are already effectively uninsurable. Meanwhile, the government's own £5.2 billion flood defence programme is [40% behind schedule](#), and expected to protect just 200,000 properties by 2027, far short of its original 336,000 target.

In the midst of these brutal realities, a national security report on biodiversity loss and ecosystem collapse, developed with input from the intelligence services, was [suppressed by Downing Street](#) for being 'too negative' - before being obtained and part-published by *The Times*. The report bleakly sets out the stakes, and in particular makes a brutal case that food resilience in this country is parlous. The [Climate Change Committee's progress reports](#) have been unequivocal: the UK is 'not yet adapted' even to current warming levels, let alone the further heating that's locked in. At 2°C, Britain faces agricultural system failure, cascading infrastructure breakdowns, and millions of homes at flood risk.

Though this is a desperate situation, we do not say it to induce despair. Rather, we want to induce action grounded in reality - including the real, [difficult emotions](#) that honest acknowledgment of the facts can produce. If we're serious about responding to the climate crisis, we have to start from where we actually are - not where we wish we were. Where we are is a country already experiencing serious climate impacts, with far worse coming, and no realistic prospect of preventing them through emissions cuts alone.

That means we need to adapt. And that word - 'adaptation' - might just be the most important word in the coming climate politics.

Let's talk about the A-word

We might as well acknowledge it: 'adaptation' is not a word that sets hearts racing. It sounds like a word in a biology textbook about lizards. It doesn't have the urgency of 'emergency' or the moral clarity of 'justice'. It sits in the same lexical neighbourhood as 'adjustment' and 'coping mechanism' - not exactly a rallying cry.

But it has advantages too. It connects with an understanding of humans as adaptable beings. It evokes Darwin's crucial understanding that we need to evolve to avoid being thrown out of our ecological niche. It is already in the lexicon of both politicians and ordinary citizens. And it needs in its interpretation to be contested, against those who would foolishly say 'We can just adapt!', making it sound as though the task is easy, when in fact the great adaptations that we need to make are as demanding as should be expected to restore a sense of national purpose.

The [SAFER report](#) (Strategic Adaptation For Emergency Resilience), published by the [Climate Majority Project](#) in 2025, calls what we're advocating 'strategic adaptation'.

What we mean (and what we don't)

Not all adaptation is equal. Air conditioning is adaptation to heat - but it increases energy demand, strains the grid, and pumps more heat into urban environments. The Thames Barrier is adaptation to storm surges - but as sea levels rise, we're approaching its design limits, and as building continues on floodplains downstream, it creates more vulnerable assets to defend. These are *reactive* measures that defer vulnerability or shift it elsewhere. That is nothing like the adaptation we need.

[Strategic adaptation](#) looks upstream and long-term. It reduces emissions and builds resilience simultaneously, strengthens communities, and creates co-benefits that people can see and feel. In doing so, it directly confronts the '[dragons of inaction](#)', those powerful psychological barriers that can keep us from taking the actions we know we need to take. The SAFER report calls this '[transformative adaptation](#)' - action that doesn't merely protect

the status quo but builds towards more comprehensive, systemic change and a better future.

But we should be honest about the tensions. There is a partly-legitimate concern - one that has kept adaptation on the margins of climate advocacy for many years - that talking about adaptation signals acceptance of failure, or worse, that it diverts attention and resources from the emissions reductions that remain desperately necessary. We don't dismiss this concern. The risk of maladaptation is real: adaptation that entrenches fossil fuel dependence, protects the wealthy at the expense of the vulnerable, or provides political cover for inaction on emissions would be worse than no adaptation at all. What we argue is not that adaptation should replace mitigation, but that strategic, community-led adaptation can *strengthen* the case for emissions reduction - by building the political constituency, social infrastructure, and lived understanding of climate reality that makes serious decarbonisation achievable. There can be a symbiotic relationship between those working on adaptation and those working on reducing emissions, fighting for every 0.01 degree of less heating. We do not undervalue the work of those who fight even in the face of impossible odds. And there is not only the space, but the need for everyone to play their part.

Moreover, the claim about accepting failure needs to be handled in a sophisticated way. Accepting a crucial degree of failure thus far *is simply truthful*. When one looks at the state of the climate COP process; or the sense in which Paris is (tragically) basically dead; when one looks at the weak ebb of climate activism and climate politics or the attempt at driving a culture-war framing of climate; and above all when one looks at graphs like this one:

Given all these things, an admission of a shockingly-large degree of failure is not only appropriate but necessary. Admitting failure can be a powerful, honest, authentic, disarming, empowering act (as one of us found, in the run-up to the first Extinction Rebellion, when [this talk](#) went viral). And admitting failure *at decarbonisation* is essential if we are to make the head-room for getting successful *at (strategic) adaptation*. We will never get serious about adaptation while we lie to ourselves that we are winning.

What we argue too is that the genie is out of the bottle. The likes of Richard Tice and [Bill Gates](#) are going big on adaptation and they won't stop talking if the rest of us stay quiet. On the contrary, they would then *own the space*. Tice's 'We can just adapt!', and his support for the maladaptations of huge concrete flood-walls or endless dredging; and Gates's adaptationist big bets on techno-'solutionism' (Stratospheric Aerosol Injection); these are bids to own the space. We cannot cede this space.

We have a narrow headstart - the hard right is still confused about climate (to deny or not to deny is the question) - and we must use it, because we've wasted too long pretending mitigation alone would spare us the need to prepare.

In the face of what is coming, we cannot delay any longer seeking to make ourselves *safer*.

What strategic adaptation looks like in practice

Photo from <https://www.retrofitbalsallheath.org/post/february-newsletter-2026>

Balsall Heath in Birmingham is a lower-income inner-city neighbourhood of Victorian terraces - exactly the kind of area that climate breakdown hits hardest and policy reaches last. It's here where local architect John Christophers built the UK's first zero-carbon retrofit home in 2009, slashing energy use by 85%. But one house, however impressive, changes nothing for the neighbourhood. So in 2022, Christophers and a coalition of local organisations - mosques, churches, community trusts, a women's hub - launched [Retrofit Balsall Heath](#). They went door-to-door across 4,900 homes. They held over 50 energy cafés, translating materials into Punjabi, Mirpuri, and Arabic.

The result: 650 homes retrofitted, with insulation, solar panels, and heat pumps. EPC ratings improved by at least one band in 75% of cases. The project won the 2023 Collaborative Partnership Award and was Highly Commended for Just Transition. But the numbers only tell part of the story. Retrofit Balsall Heath [put it simply](#): retrofit is about homes, neighbourhoods, hearts and minds. The mosque congregations, the women's hub members, the community trust volunteers who drove this project are not people who would typically attend a climate march or respond to a net zero campaign. Yet they are now active participants in the climate response. Adaptation, done this way, doesn't just build warmer homes. It builds a bigger movement. And of course, in the form of retrofit, it's a big

win-win-win: quality of life is improved, bills are lower, insulation against hot summers and cold winters gained, and emissions reduced.

The [Yorkshire Peat Partnership's Pennines restoration](#) sequesters carbon whilst reducing flood risk for Hebden Bridge. The Wicken Fen Vision in Cambridgeshire is creating a 53-square-kilometre wetland that reduces flood risk whilst providing habitat and sequestering carbon. The [Eden Rivers Trust](#) in Cumbria restores natural river processes, allowing rivers to flood onto floodplains rather than channelling water towards towns. Each of these integrates decarbonisation and nature-positivity and resilience. Each produces visible, local benefits. Each gives people a reason to act that begins with their own street, their own river, their own landscape.

Why adaptation mobilises people when other messaging doesn't

The [SAFER report](#) identifies several mechanisms through which adaptation drives broader climate engagement.

First, adaptation confronts what the report calls 'soft denial' - the still widespread assumption that current mitigation efforts plus future tech will prevent really serious climate damage. While outright climate denial has declined, this softer complacency persists in the public narrative that leaders 'have got this', decarbonisation is in hand and, if there are gaps, we'll produce new technology to avert the worst. Visible adaptation efforts, honestly undertaken and presented, challenge this: adapting to harm is incompatible with the belief that harm will be bypassed or will just evaporate. This is not guaranteed to produce engagement rather than fatalism - the effect depends on the context (on which, read on) - but the evidence from communities where adaptation is happening suggests that, given the right conditions, it encourages a sense of agency rather than despair.

Second, adaptation addresses a critical failure of the 'information deficit model' - the assumption that giving people enough facts about the climate threat will produce engagement. [Research consistently shows](#) that public information alone can cause overwhelm and disengagement, when it comes to climate. Adaptation provides something the facts alone can't: a social context in which climate reality can be received without producing paralysis. When people respond actively and meaningfully to a concrete threat,

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within communities where they feel mutual support and shared concern, the conditions for sustained engagement, rather than sustained despair, are created.

Third, and perhaps most importantly for movement strategy, adaptation hugely broadens who participates. Decarbonisation messaging has become prone to political polarisation, limiting engagement especially among working-class and marginalised communities. A Conservative councillor and a Green activist can both support intelligent flood defences. A farmer sceptical of climate alarmism will restore hedgerows if it stops topsoil washing away. When Henley-on-Thames's town council passed a unanimous vote of no confidence in Thames Water, it wasn't a Green initiative - it was the Conservative mayor who proposed the motion. Adaptation creates common ground because it addresses what people can see and feel.

This is the opposite of throwing soup at paintings. Although [disruptive tactics can succeed in raising the alarm](#), they can also [polarise and narrow the movement's base](#). Adaptation meets people where they are, inviting them in through their own concerns. It offers a way to act that makes sense on its own terms, regardless of where people sit on the political spectrum.

From outrage to agency: Greener Henley

The journey from an initial grievance through anger to community organising is well illustrated in Henley-on-Thames and the work of volunteer-led charity, [Greener Henley](#). The town has been recognised both nationally and internationally for its community action on clean water, helped by public fury over Thames Water's sewage discharges - 72 billion litres pumped into the River Thames between 2020 and 2023 - into a sustained programme of community action.

Greener Henley's achievements are concrete. A [Schools Climate and Nature Action Network](#) now includes 17 local schools, with a pioneering 'Green Futures Awards' programme and an annual Schools Science Fair. 'Big Green Conversation' events have brought together hydrologists, Olympic rowers, insurance experts, and flood scientists with residents wanting to understand what climate change means for their town. The [Nature Squared](#) programme is creating pollinator habitats across the town, a ['pay as you go' car club](#) aims to reduce individual car ownership, and citizen scientists test river water quality weekly - a May 2025 reading showed E. coli levels five times the satisfactory threshold, providing hard

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evidence for campaigning.

Greener Henley now has an explicit goal of engaging 5,000 people - around a quarter of the local population - by 2028. Oxfordshire County Council's Climate Outreach Officer has described them as 'a trailblazer in community-led climate and nature action'.

Photo from <https://greenerhenley.org.uk/protect-our-river/>

What makes Greener Henley instructive for movement strategy is its pathway. It began with nature restoration and schools engagement and expanded into flood resilience planning. It is now producing a community that thinks and acts in climate terms across multiple dimensions of town life - from schools to rowing clubs to local businesses. The rowing clubs care because red board days are increasing. The businesses care because flooding threatens profits. The parents care because their children got sick after swimming. None of this required anyone to sign up to climate framing. The climate understanding emerged from the adaptation work, not the other way round.

How adaptation creates political will

Research on climate communication reveals [an important finding](#) for movement strategy. Experiencing climate impacts does not automatically increase support for climate policy. What matters is '[subjective attribution](#)' - whether people connect their experience to human-caused climate change, and whether they believe collective action can make a

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difference. This depends on the social and organisational context of the experience: whether people have a community around them that names what is happening, provides a framework for understanding it, and offers a path to a meaningful response.

This is where the [first paper in our series on extreme weather events](#) connects directly with this one. Extreme weather creates a moment of heightened attention and receptivity - a political window. But that window closes quickly unless organised communities are ready to act within it. Adaptation-organising provides exactly this infrastructure. When communities have already been working together on flood resilience or retrofit, they have the relationships, the knowledge, and the narrative framework to turn the next extreme weather event into sustained political engagement rather than fleeting outrage (which can even take a counter-productive conspiratorial or cynical form).

The political pressure that adaptation-agency creates is qualitatively different from the kind that abstract emissions targets can achieve. After the July 2021 London floods, Transport for London [faced fierce questioning](#) about infrastructure resilience. After the 2022 heatwaves [buckled railway tracks](#), Transport Secretary Grant Shapps acknowledged that infrastructure 'built for a certain climate' was failing in a changed one. A politician can justify delaying net zero by citing costs. They cannot easily justify leaving constituents unprotected from the next flood. This is why [Friends of the Earth have issued a legal challenge](#) - in the High Court and subsequently the European Court of Human Rights - framing adaptation as a basic governmental duty: to protect British lives and livelihoods. This follows earlier successful legal action by Friends of the Earth, as discussed [here](#) by the Climate Majority Project and partners.

Projects like Retrofit Balsall Heath or Greener Henley show what competent adaptation action looks like. They provide a standard against which government inaction can be measured. And the gap between what government knows and what it does - exemplified by the [suppressed security report](#) on ecological breakdown - is a political vulnerability that organised communities are well-placed to exploit.

Perhaps most crucially, adaptation builds the social cohesion, trust and structures - mutual aid networks, shared knowledge, collective confidence - that help people weather crises together. After the [2019 Fishlake floods](#), residents organised their own relief when the official response was slow. Those networks remain, creating ongoing resilience that no flood wall can replicate. When people see adaptation improving their lives, they become

receptive to deeper transformation. The Balsall Heath residents who watched their neighbourhood change aren't just warmer in winter. They're part of something. And that sense of agency, of collective capacity to respond, is what builds the infrastructure of movements.

The path forward

The [majority of Britons already care](#) about climate and ecosystems. What they have lacked is a way to act that feels meaningful, achievable, and connected to their daily lives. Strategic adaptation and resilience-building provides that. It doesn't ask people to buy into abstract future benefits. It asks them to protect their streets, their neighbours, their food supply, their rivers - and shows them it's possible.

For the potential of strategic adaptation to be realised, three things need to change.

- **For campaign strategists and movement organisers:** Make (strategic) adaptation a primary lens for climate campaigning. This means building campaigns around the threats people experience now - flooding, heat, water stress, food price shocks - and connecting them to systemic causes and solutions. It means supporting and amplifying community-led adaptation projects rather than trying to recruit communities into pre-existing campaign structures. The [SAFER report](#)'s framework of 'four dimensions of climate action' - **awareness of reality, access to meaningful action, emotional support, and a sense of being part of a capable movement** - provides a useful framework for campaign design. Campaigns that address all four dimensions will mobilise far more effectively than those relying on information and urgency alone.

Organisers should recognise that adaptation expands the movement's constituency in ways that most existing tactics cannot. The mosque congregations in Balsall Heath are a remarkable example, as are the rowing clubs in Henley, the farmers restoring hedgerows in Yorkshire - these are climate actors, whether or not they use that language. Meeting them on their own terms, rather than asking them to adopt the existing movement's framing, is how the base grows. Greener Henley's approach is instructive: start with what people already care about, build community capacity to respond, and let broader climate understanding develop organically

through the work.

- **For funders and philanthropic foundations:** Climate philanthropy has overwhelmingly prioritised mitigation-focused campaigns and policy work. The evidence suggests that community-led adaptation projects produce outsized returns in engagement and political will relative to their cost. As is [repeatedly said by campaigners](#), what these projects need is sustained, multi-year core funding - not project-by-project grants that consume capacity in applications and reporting.

Funders should prioritise projects that integrate emissions reduction with resilience-building and nature-restoration, that are community-led rather than imposed, and that have the potential to replicate. The [Retrofit Reimagined](#) festivals - run in Bristol, London, Glasgow, and Machynlleth, asking what the climate transition would look like if it were designed, owned, and governed by the people who live there - show how successful models can spread. They need resources to do it more and faster.

- **For policymakers:** The [Climate Change Committee](#) has repeatedly assessed the UK's adaptation preparations as inadequate. [Friends of the Earth's legal challenge](#) has framed adaptation as a basic governmental duty. The government's own [suppressed security report](#) revealed warnings severe enough that Downing Street blocked its publication. The gap between what the government knows and what it does is a political vulnerability that campaigns can and must exploit. Demand National Adaptation Plans that go beyond reactive defence, and that are funded with mission-like seriousness. Ring-fence funding for local authority adaptation. End building on floodplains. Make effective adaptation a litmus test for political seriousness on climate. The political logic is straightforward: communities that have organised around adaptation will hold their representatives accountable in ways that abstract emissions targets never could.

In conclusion

Britain is not prepared for what's coming. The floods will worsen. Heatwaves will intensify. Agricultural systems will face escalating shocks. The question is not whether we adapt, but how - and whether adaptation becomes a force for justice and solidarity, or a scramble in which the most vulnerable are neglected.

The communities already confronting climate reality are demonstrating something that decades of climate campaigning have struggled to achieve: broad-based, locally rooted, politically potent engagement with the climate crisis that crosses traditional divides. They are discovering collective power, demanding accountability, and building something worth defending. Adaptation done well doesn't retreat from the ambition of emissions reduction. It synergises with it: it builds the constituency, the political will, and the social infrastructure that could finally make serious decarbonisation achievable.

[It's time to talk about adaptation](#) - or whatever we end up calling it. Loudly, strategically, and with the urgency the moment demands. For this is the age of adaptation. If we don't shape how that looks, climate impacts will shape it for us.

This is the second in a series of climate discussion papers from [Social Change Lab](#). The first examined how [extreme weather events](#) create windows for political change.

About Social Change Lab

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